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Solzhenitsyn's One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich: The Human Survival under Stalinist Injustice and Its Traces on the Biographical Accounts of the Writer

Ivan Denisovich Shukhov was imprisoned for about eight years of a ten-year sentence. Thus, textual evidence proves it: "According to his dossier, Ivan Denisovich Shukov had been sentenced for high treason. He had testified to it himself. Yes, he had surrendered to the Germans with the intention of betraying his country, and he had returned from captivity to carry out a mission for German intelligence" (One Day, p.28). In the Russian concentration camp, his situation is horrible with inadequate food, warm clothes, and heat in frigid conditions. But he cannot think of the future because his prison term could be extended if the authorities brought him up on another charge. Shukhov can only think about the present and how he can survive for one more day.

The innocent Ivan, who refused to accept the injustices of the system that had sent him guiltless into the labor camps. In the labor camp, Ivan Denisovich battles for human survival in a Stalinist injustice. Perhaps as a victim, his only and most treasured and valued goal is to stay alive. And from this state, he is thinking whether religious faith is still necessary for his survival. This was the question playing on his mind while dealing with this unbearable, inhuman servitude of his life, but in the end, Ivan deeply pondered that faith is the only way that saves him after all the miserable life he had encountered. Ivan Denisovich Shukov was one of far too many who had the misfortune to escape and be captured by the Nazis and make it back to his lines only to be imprisoned in a gulag, a work camp, for his efforts.

Survival is a task that needs Ivan to prioritize. Caesar Markovich can survive only as long as his packages arrive. The Captain, if he survives solitary confinement, will have to give up his unrealistic ideas about communism and his overbearing manner if he wants to live. Alyosha the Baptist is, by the very nature of his faith, more interested in an afterlife than his physical survival during this lifetime. Fetyukov and most of the inmates will not live long.

Only Ivan combines all the qualities necessary to survive: he works for himself and for his comrades, but not for the authorities; he does not rely on outside help, but on his skill and craftiness; he used to obey sensible orders; he has faith, but it is a faith designed to help him cope with the realities of his life. Ivan believes in the strength and the dignity of the simple Russian worker and peasant without being a Communist. Furthermore, the population of

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Ivan's prison camp contains different individuals of Russian society, and most of them were victims of Stalinist injustice. Some prisoners represent the professional, social, and ethnic groups in the Soviet Union. When he was only twenty-seven, Solzhenitsyn was also a victim of Stalinist injustice and was thrown into prison because of "counterrevolutionary activity" and was sentenced to eight years of forced labor and exile by one of Stalin's infamous troikas, courts consisting of three military judges. After first serving in a correctional labor camp and then in a prison research institute near Moscow, the author was finally sent to a special camp in the mining region of Kazakhstan, because, as he claims, he would not make moral compromises with the secret police. It was there, in Siberia, that he conceived of the idea of writing *One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich*; like the hero of the novel, "Solzhenitsyn had to wear his prison number stamped on the areas of the forehead of his cap, as well as on the heart, the knees, and the back of his uniform. Henceforth, the author attempts to show a literary-autobiographical record that exposes his encounter with the voluminous personal testimony of other inmates that he collected and committed to memory during his imprisonment.

Correspondingly, Solzhenitsyn would also like to show the Soviet system during the Stalin era. In the whole system, there are chronic food shortages, except for a privileged few who can bribe their way out of corrupt officials. There is bureaucratic inefficiency, leading to waste and sabotage. To dispel any doubt that all this applies only to camp life, which is barely reflected in what Ivan wished to happen. The men there have bribed the officials to relieve them from farm work so they can paint the profitable, sleazy carpets. In addition, there is also the constant spying and informing activities which are typical of Soviet society, and Solzhenitsyn deplors them most of all, for they create distrust among people who should cooperate with the authorities rather than against themselves. A prisoner is another prisoner's worst enemy, not the authorities. It is interesting to note that, in spite of serving ten- or twenty-five-year sentences, all of the prisoners seem to be serving life terms. Nobody is ever released from the larger Soviet prison; when one term ends, another one is added on or even more. Solzhenitsyn sees as little possibility for a successful, violent overthrow of the Soviet regime as he does for an armed revolt in Ivan's camp. The real hope is that the corrupt, inefficient system will destroy itself from within and that Russia will return to a system that is founded on the qualities which Ivan represents: hard work without too much reliance on modernity.

Lesson:

- Faith is the only necessary shield that saves us from unbearable, inhumane conditions; without it, we are doomed.
- Writer "cannot put himself today in the service of those who make history; he is at the service of those who suffer it." -Albert Camus.

Reference:

Solzhenitsyn, Aleksandr., trans. Parker, Ryan (1963). *One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich*. New York: Penguin Books USA.